

Multispectral versus Hyperspectral Imaging for Crop Separability

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Abstract

Recognizing and classifying crops using satellite-based remote sensing is important for reliable agricultural monitoring and precision farming. This study evaluates the performance of two imaging technologies—multispectral and hyperspectral—in distinguishing crop types under varying conditions. The Mahalanobis distance is employed as a separability metric and applied to annotated data. We compare hyperspectral imagery from PRISMA with multispectral data from Sentinel-2, focusing on a test region across different months of the year. The results demonstrate that PRISMA’s hyperspectral data generally achieves superior separability compared to Sentinel-2. However, factors such as vegetation canopy and spatial resolution can influence the results. These findings highlight the advantages of hyperspectral, but also the situations in which multispectral can be a reliable substitute.

Keywords— Mahalanobis Distance, PRISMA, Sentinel-2, Crop Monitoring, Precision Agriculture

1 Introduction

A critical factor in ensuring food security is the continuous progress of agricultural systems. Precision agriculture has grown significantly, with remote sensing emerging as a key technology. In a review on the topic, Mohyuddin et al. [1] argues on the need of intelligent and automated farming. A critical step towards this direction is the automatic crop recognition classification and separation; it enables applications like yield estimation, crop monitoring, land cover mapping, and drought or flood stress detection [2].

Complementing these advancements, remote sensing (RS) has emerged as a cornerstone technology, driven by the increasing availability of high-resolution satellite imagery. Specifically, it is important for crop monitoring and within this direction, one important applications is crop classification. Accurate crop classification involves identifying and mapping different crop types based on their spectral, spatial, and temporal characteristics. Effective classification of different crop types requires ensuring that the input data possesses a high degree of separability between classes. Separability refers to the extent to which data points from different classes (e.g. wheat, corn, beans) can be distinguished based on their features.

Numerous studies analyzed and aimed to improve the accuracy of crop prediction by considering factors such as vegetation development stage, optimal feature sets, etc [2]. However, in this paper, we adopt a statistical approach to explore the underlying patterns in the data. Specifically, we analyze the raw data distribution and calculate the Average Mahalanobis Distance (AMD) for each data point belonging to a particular class. This quantifies how closely data points align with their class’s central tendency, revealing the dataset’s separability.

The discussion focuses on the data acquisition methods employed by two instruments: the Multispectral Instrument (MSI) aboard the Sentinel-2 satellite and the Hyperspectral Instrument (HSI) aboard the PRISMA satellite. The AMD is applied to compare the results provided by the two data types, with the goal of understanding the relationship between the amount of available information and improved class separability in agricultural datasets.

To ensure the relevance of these differences, the study tracks the data across different plant development stages, focusing on the months of March, May, and June, 2024. These moments are relevant for the vegetation stages of agricultural crops.

The images were acquired within a similar date range to minimize the impact of vegetation phenological changes and atmospheric conditions. However, aligning image acquisition dates from different sensors, particularly spaceborn ones, poses a challenge due to differences in their revisit intervals and orbit.

Multispectral sensors capture data across a limited range of the electromagnetic spectrum, typically with five to ten broad bands, including RGB and a few infrared bands. For instance, Sentinel-2’s MSI offers 13 spectral bands, including 10-meter bands for land cover monitoring, 20-meter red-edge bands for plant health, and SWIR bands for moisture detection, with a 5-day revisit frequency. Additionally, its 60-meter atmospheric correction bands enhance the accuracy of surface reflectance measurements. [3].

In contrast, hyperspectral sensors collect data across hundreds of narrow spectral bands (10-20 nm), offering much finer spectral resolution. The PRISMA hyperspectral camera captures two spectral ranges, VIS/NIR and NIR/SWIR, covering a total of 239 bands (66 in VIS/NIR and 173 in NIR/SWIR), with a spatial resolution of 30 meters per pixel. The satellite operates in a sun-synchronous orbit at an altitude of approximately 615 km, providing a swath width of 30 km. With a repeat orbital cycle of about 29 days, PRISMA can acquire images of areas up to 1000 km apart in a single pass, effectively reducing the revisit time to less than one week. [4].

1.1 Related work

Our work aims to compare homogeneity and heterogeneity while describing crops with multispectral Sentinel data and respectively PRISMA hyperspectral data. The tool used for analysis is the Mahalanobis Distance (MD) and, thus we will review works in both directions.

With respect to comparison between multispectral and hyperspectral imaging, in recent period several works performed comparative analysis in specific themes. Jarocińska et al. [5] compare the proficiency of identification of Nature-2000 sites using multispectral data from Sentinel-2 with hyperspectral data from HySpex VNIR-1800 and SWIR-384 scanners and found that highest accuracy is with hyperspectral data, yet multispectral is potentially better for mires and heaths; their approach is based on Linear Discriminant Analysis and resulted in 20% difference in favor of hyperspectral. Sedighi et al. [6] used Principal Component Analysis as data selection followed by Particle Swarm Optimization for classification in identification of sugar canes type in Iran using multispectral Landsat ETM data and respectively EO-1 Hyperion hyperspectral; their findings showed, again better accuracy is from hyperspectral data. Jung et al. [7] compare the efficiency of using multispectral and hyperspectral data for estimation of

Figure 1: The RGB visualization of two satellite images (hyperspectral - PRISMA and, respectively, multispectral - Sentinel-2) taken in March, along with their corresponding masks.

Suspended Sediment Concentration and found better results with hyperspectral data.

Overall, the amount of works into this direction is limited and also the number problems envisaged is finite. Comparison for crop separation, has not, to our best knowledge approached.

As said, the method is based on MD. This metric has been used before to analyze remotely sensed acquired data. For instance, such an approach is utilized by Li et al. [8], who employ a modified version of MD in conjunction with Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) to classify time-series data from wetland areas. MD is particularly valuable in this context as it enables the quantification of similarity across high-dimensional spaces, accounting for the covariance structure of the data. This adaptation of MD further motivates its fitness for scenarios with sparse temporal data, such as satellite imagery captured at irregular intervals.

MD has been effectively utilized in crop classification. For example, Azmir et al. [9] successfully employed MD to classify tobacco crops by the end of June in the north-western region of Pakistan, achieving a classification accuracy of 75.26% without the application of post-processing techniques. García-Santillán and Pajares [10] use MD to separate crop from weed in images of maize fields.

Figure 2: The Average Mahalanobis Distance (AMD): a cell $= (row, column)$ in a matrix represent the averaged distance from all pixels from the *row* crop w.r.t the distribution formed by pixels from *column* crop. On March data, crop in a very early vegetation stage are marked; in a RGB satellite image, an observer, will label them rather as “bare soil”.

2 Method and materials

2.1 Data

The study area is situated near Braşov, Romania, encompassing a variety of agricultural lands with over 17 different crop types. The multispectral satellite data used for this study is publicly available online at <https://zenodo.org/records/14283243> and part of the μ DACIA5 dataset [11]. We have considered three moments in which we made the comparison; this number resulted by intersecting the period of the year in which multiple crops are available, with the moment when a PRISMA image has been recorded and it had a good quality (i.e. area not covered by clouds).

The image captured by the PRISMA satellite covers approximately 68 km², while the Sentinel-2 image encompasses a smaller area of approximately 32 km². The spatial resolution of the Sentinel-2 image is 10 meters per pixel, whereas the resolution of the PRISMA image is 30 meters per pixel. Only the overlapping area between the two images have been considered. Therefore, the images have been registered and cropped accordingly.

Two samples of images rendered in RGB colorspace along with their corresponding masks may be seen in the Figure 1. The study analyzed eight distinct types of vegetation, including *winter wheat*, *spring wheat*, *corn*, *pea*, *potato*, *sugar beets*, *alfalfa*, and *grassland*. This information about the crop has been in-situ verified [11]. Only species that had already germinated and exhibited higher NDVI values were selected for analysis each month. Therefore, we noted the absence of *potatoes* and *corn* in the month of March.

As highlighted by Masini et al. [12], hyperspectral images, due to their large data volume, cannot be effectively used without the preliminary removal of “bad bands”. In this study, this process was carried out in ENVI (Environment for Visualizing Images)

using IDL (Interactive Data Language). After this process we are left with 187 out of the 239 original bands.

2.2 Mahalanobis Distance

The Mahalanobis distance is a measure of the distance between a point \mathbf{x} and a distribution \mathcal{Q} ; often the distribution \mathcal{Q} is assumed to be multivariate Gaussian of μ mean and Σ covariance matrix. It is calculated as follows:

$$MD(\mathbf{x}, \mathcal{Q}_{\mu, \Sigma}) = \sqrt{(\mathbf{x} - \mu)^T \Sigma^{-1} (\mathbf{x} - \mu)} \quad (1)$$

The MD is a multivariate generalization of the square of the standard score computed as:

$$z = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \quad (2)$$

which is how many standard deviations away x is from the mean of \mathcal{Q} . This property makes it suitable to compare compactness and sparsity among clusters originating in differently dimensional spaces such as the 13-dimensional multispectral and respectively 187-hyperspectral. Our study aims to measure how compactly pixels from the same crop cluster and how far they are from other crops, in both multispectral and hyperspectral spaces.

In such a case, in eq. (1) \mathbf{x} is a pixel marked in a query crop, μ is the center of cluster of pixels from reference crop, and Σ^{-1} is the inverse of the covariance matrix of cluster of the reference crop.

To have a statistical measure, the distances from all pixels, i of the query crop to the reference crop are summed and the average is calculated:

$$AMD = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n MD_i \quad (3)$$

Where MD_i is the Mahalanobis distance between each point and the center of of the reference cluster.

To evaluate compactness and sparsity for all agricultural crops, we compute the MD between each pixel belonging to Crop k and the center of Crop j , where $j, k \in \{1, 2, \dots, C\}$ and C is the total number of crops. The distance is given by:

$$MD_i^{(k,j)} = \sqrt{(\mathbf{x}_i^{(k)} - \mu_j)^T \Sigma_i^{-1} (\mathbf{x}_i^{(k)} - \mu_j)} \quad (4)$$

Here, $\mathbf{x}_i^{(k)}$ is the i -th data point corresponding to Crop k , μ_j is the center of Crop j , while Σ_i^{-1} is the inverse of the covariance matrix specific of Crop k .

The distances are computed for all $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n_k\}$, where n_k is the number of points in Crop k . The average Mahalanobis distance (AMD) between Crop k and Crop j is then calculated as:

$$AMD_{k,j} = \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{i=1}^{n_k} D_i^{(k,j)} \quad (5)$$

This process is repeated for all pairs of crops (k, j) , providing a comprehensive measure of the separability between different agricultural crops. In our case, the distance is computed on the Sentinel images and respectively on the PRISMA images; we need to ensure that the same are exists in both images, but since we compare a statistical significant measure (i.e. average), there is no need for the two images to be registered.

Figure 3: Visualization of March data from crops in early vegetation stages: spring wheat, pea, sugar beet. We plot, for each crop of $[\mu - \sigma; \mu + \sigma]$ range for spectral band. Both, the multispectral (left) and hyperspectral (right) show overlapping ranges over much spectral bands.

Figure 4: Visualization using LDA of March data from crops in early vegetation stages. In the multispectral (left) separability is poor, while in the hyperspectral (right) is much better.

3 Implementation and results

The code has been implemented in Python and the functions used in the linear algebra were provided by `numpy` library.

Obtained results are presented numerically and graphically in Figure 2. Revisiting equation (2), one will find out that crops with sparse pixels (small AMD, because large Σ) include pixels from other crops, while tightly clustered crops produce large values. Small main diagonal values signal tight clusters without outliers, whereas large values indicate many outliers. Main diagonal values smaller than non-diagonal ones suggest homogeneous in-crop representation and, respectively, heterogeneous representation of different crops, indicating good crop separability.

Analyzing the results from Figure 2, some observations can be made:

- (i) A prominent visual observation is the asymmetry in the MD matrices, indicating that the distance values can vary significantly depending on the crop used as the reference or subject of the comparison. This asymmetry is particularly evident in the PRISMA data for March, where the *spring wheat* – *sugar beets* pair records the highest distance, a result that is not mirrored in the reversed pair. This phenomenon suggests a difference in the covariance of the crops selected. Specifically, *spring wheat* exhibits a higher covariance matrix (i.e. large eigenvalues, thus, large trace), which implies a stronger dependency between its spectral values, a dependency that is absent in the reversed pair.

In contrast, in March, Sentinel-2 data shows higher distance values for *grassland* and *winter wheat* compared to other crop pairs, unlike PRISMA. This is, likely, due to Sentinel-2’s higher spatial resolution and the contrast created by bare soil. The pronounced separability of the *pea*–*grassland* pair reflects the low green area of *pea* contrasting with *grassland*’s high green coverage during this period.

- (ii) The Mahalanobis Distances derived from PRISMA data are consistently higher than those from Sentinel-2, highlighting the enhanced discriminative power of hyperspectral data. This difference is particularly evident when comparing crops that are challenging to differentiate using the coarser spectral bands of Sentinel-2. For example, in March, the MD between *pea* and *sugar beets* is 59.28 for

PRISMA, compared to only 3.84 for Sentinel-2, indicating that distinguishing these crops is considerably more difficult with Sentinel-2. In the later case, the distance from *pea* to *pea* is smaller.

- (iii) The greatest Mahalanobis distances were observed between crops with distinct spectral characteristics, such as for the *spring wheat –sugar beet* pair. These findings align with expectations, as these crops exhibit significant differences in both texture and spectral reflectance. For example, in March, PRISMA shows a Mahalanobis distance of 357.02 between sugar beets and spring wheat, whereas Sentinel-2 records a much lower value of 6.32.
- (iv) An interesting observation arises when comparing the impact of the seasonal transition from March to May on the quality of Sentinel-2 and PRISMA data. It appears that the change from March to May had a more significant effect on Sentinel-2 than on PRISMA, which warrants further discussion.

4 Conclusions

In this study, we observed that Mahalanobis Distances varied significantly depending on the crop selected as the reference or subject of comparison. In particular, PRISMA data demonstrated higher MD values, indicating superior discriminative power over Sentinel-2, especially when distinguishing crops with similar spectral characteristics. For example, the MD between sugar beets and peas was much higher in PRISMA than in Sentinel-2. Additionally, crops with distinct spectral properties, such as spring wheat and sugar beets, exhibited the greatest MD values, further emphasizing the advantages of hyperspectral data. Finally, the seasonal transition from March to May had a more pronounced impact on Sentinel-2 data, suggesting that PRISMA's higher spectral resolution provides more stable and accurate results across different growth stages.

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